

USING DIFFERENT METHODS IN ORGANIZING MUSIC LESSONS.

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Annotation: This article is about reforms in the field of culture and art in our country, the role of music in the life of society, the role of music in the formation of the spiritual, artistic and moral culture of the young generation, the methods of organizing music lessons by teachers of music culture. detailed information is provided.

Keywords: music, culture, manners, national pride, lesson, teacher, creativity, skills, education.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada yurtimizdagi madaniyat, san'at sohasidagi islohotlar, musiqaning jamiyat hayotidagi tutgan o'rni, yosh-avlodni ma'naviy, badiiy va axloqiy madaniyatini shakllantirishda musiqaning o'rni, musiqa madaniyati o'qituvchilari tomonidan musiqa darslarini tashkil etish usullari haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: musiqa, madaniyat, odob, milliy g'urur, dars, o'qituvchi, ijod, mahorat, tarbiya.

Аннотация: В данной статье речь идет о реформах в сфере культуры и искусства в нашей стране, роли музыки в жизни общества, роли музыки в формировании духовной, художественной и нравственной культуры молодого поколения, методах организации занятий музыкой учителями музыкальной культуры. Приведена подробная информация.

Ключевые слова: музыка, культура, нравы, национальная гордость, урок, учитель, творчество, умения, образование.

National pride and patriotism of music class students to implement education, creative skills, sophistication and artistic taste serves to grow, expand the range of thought, and nurture independence and initiative. Accordingly, the room allocated for the music lesson should be spacious, the light should fall on the children from the left side, and the air should be fresh.

The room must be equipped with necessary items. An equal half of the board should have a sheet of music. In the room there should be a musical instrument, if possible, a piano, as well as a tape recorder or diskette player, and a set of magnetic tapes and diskettes with recorded works for listening to music and group singing for all classes. Posters, tests, control work, solfeggio and singing are also in the room it is necessary to have a wardrobe to put and store the collections. [1] To create acoustic conditions, the corners of the classroom are covered with curtains-screens made of fabric. Room portraits of children's

composers, state symbols on the walls, hang curtains on the windows that do not interfere with the light should be placed. Putting all the equipment in the classroom in its place, the appearance should be so beautiful that the student enters the classroom let him feel like entering a concert hall when he arrives. But the room it is not necessary to decorate it too much.

A music lesson should be clearly and orderly organized from the moment students enter the classroom until the end of the lesson and when they leave the classroom. If possible, when the bell rings, children line up in front of the classroom door and enter the classroom to the sound of music. It is important to define each child's place in the classroom. [2] If the teacher is not familiar with the student's musical ability, at the beginning of the school year, it is necessary to put a short child in the front row, and a tall child in the back row. During the lessons, the teacher places a child with insufficient musical ability in the front row close to him and a stronger student between the students with insufficient musical ability. In music lessons, children mostly sit and practice. But it is also appropriate to sing while standing in the development of vocal and choral skills. This will give students a break, because sitting all the time during the lesson will tire the child. Starting from the first lesson, the teacher explains to the children the need to maintain peace during the lesson and observe the rules of sitting and standing in the lesson. He also monitors that this rule is not violated. Each student goes to his permanent position until the teacher stops playing and greets the students.

He waits without sitting. After the music stops, the teacher greets after giving permission to sit down, the students sit down and the music lesson starts. It is also worth mentioning that it is not a permanent rule that my child regularly enters the classroom to the sound of a march (music), only this method forms the child to walk correctly to the music of the march. This is when the subjects are easy to learn to step to the music due to these, in free time from classes and morning gymnastics can be formed even while exercising. [3] High entering and leaving the classroom will be like normal lessons without music. Pupils should answer the questions asked by the teacher only when they are allowed to raise their hands. Also students start singing only at the teacher's signal and must always remember to stop. The teacher should place the instrument, especially the piano, in such a place that the teacher playing it can be seen by all the children.

If the students deliberately distort the song, try to break the order, the teacher should not make a single mistake in taking measures against these

children. The teacher is very demanding, but at the same time, his demands should be fair and impartial to the students. However, it is not good to be too demanding and push the child seriously and under fear. Sometimes the teacher may not "notice" my child's small gaiety, he may deviate from the lesson and joke with childish words in order to give the children some rest. The volume of the teacher's voice during the lesson is also important. [4] It is a big mistake if a teacher gets angry about something, speaks rudely, quickly and rudely, shouts a little, even hits the table with his fist and says that he can scare the child and establish good discipline in this way. will have done. This false demand destroys the teacher's reputation, the student's love for science turns off. The teacher for the student's deliberate indiscipline he should remember that he should reduce the punishment as much as possible punishment makes children angry, they get on the teacher's nerves tries to touch. These actions do not lead to good.

Self-restrained, stable, never yelling at children who speaks slowly, uniformly in the spirit of friendship, put by himself strive to achieve consistent fulfillment of your request Discipline and order are always good in the teacher's class. Poor discipline in the classroom is often the teacher's classroom it comes from not knowing how to lead. [5] Therefore, the teacher he should find the mistakes he made in the lesson processes, search for the right method to use in the lesson. If a good creative situation has been created in the class, the violation of discipline by some students will anger most students. For example, when the children are singing their favorite song, one of the students will suddenly deliberately start the song early, or make a mistake in the words, or shout at a low pitch. And the teacher is forced to stop raw, to break the creative spirit in children. In this case, it is natural for the class to angrily reprimand the child who violates discipline.

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